

Open letter on projected futures in the context of sustainable development and climate change

Dear colleagues,

We are the authors of Chapter 3 “Projected futures in the context of sustainable development and climate change” of the Working Group III on Mitigation of Climate Change of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Seventh Assessment Report. As part of this chapter, we are mandated to assess a broad and diverse range of quantitative and qualitative projected futures. The [approved outline](#) of the chapter specifically mentions global and national mitigation and development pathways.

We would greatly appreciate it if you could inform us about the scenarios, pathways and futures you have developed, along with the associated publications. As communicated by the [IPCC Secretariat to the IPCC Focal Points and Ministries of Foreign Affairs](#), IPCC will not be relying on a single scenario database for the Seventh Assessment Report. To facilitate consideration of all relevant literature and scenarios, we follow the [open letter of the authors of Working Groups I, II, and III](#), and for our chapter invite researchers to:

- Archive the underlying information on scenarios, pathways, and futures from peer-reviewed publications, especially published after 2021, in a format that enables assessment (e.g., in online supplementary material or data repositories, with metadata and units clearly specified, following FAIR principles, and, if possible, using the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC) [data template](#), following the latest common definitions [see [GitHub](#) or as an [Excel file](#)]).
- Inform us about the relevant peer-reviewed publications, pre-prints, project- or publication-related scenario data, or community databases by filling a brief [survey](#).
- For qualitative scenarios and futures, inform us about the relevant peer-reviewed publications, pre-prints, reports etc. by filling this specialized [survey](#).
- If possible, submit the data underlying the scenarios to community databases, such as [Scenario Compass Initiative](#) for global emissions scenarios or [IAMC Working Group on National Scenarios](#) for regional and national emissions scenarios. Community databases facilitate assessment by ensuring common reporting standards (e.g., consistent variables definitions, units, and data formats), hence allowing us to efficiently assess information from multiple models and studies to produce a comprehensive assessment.

For the First Order Draft of the WGIII contribution to the Seventh Assessment Report, we can consider submissions until **29 September 2026**. Scenarios submitted later than this date will be considered for the Second Order Draft in 2027. A more detailed timeline will follow when the timeline for the Second Order Draft will be decided.

Please note that while submissions will enable and support consideration of literature by the authors, it does not guarantee that any particular scenario will be explicitly included in the assessment or highlighted in any specific figure or table.

With best wishes,

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